

The Role of Hate Speech, of Djamel Ben Ismail Killing Accident during the Algerian Forest Fires in August 2021. A Content Descriptive Analytical Study of Echorouk Newspaper

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Abstract

This scientific study aims to identify the methods and methods of media treatment adopted by Echorouk newspaper in dealing with the phenomenon of the escalation of hate speech. Which caused the brutal killing of a young man and the abuse of his body, coinciding with the burning of forests that Algeria witnessed in the summer of 2021, through an analysis of its publications during the month of August of the same year. Our study seeks to uncover important points, most notably knowing the reasons for the escalation of hate speech and the heinous crimes that resulted from it, starting from setting fires in forests, and ending with a brutal murder on ethnic grounds, and knowing the actors who emerged during these events, and the nature of the roles they played, The results of these events and their repercussions on the individual and society, in all fields: economic, political, and psychological. And social. The study also aims to shed light on the form and content of the media material, the templates through which it was presented, and the sources of information adopted by Echorouk daily.

Keywords: *Hate Speech, Forest Fires, Echorouk Newspaper.*

FOREWORD

The escalation of hate speech in recent decades in Algeria has become a real concern. This phenomenon has spread frighteningly, in light of the excessive use of social media, which has been exploited to create and disseminate this type of toxic speech on a wide scale, which threatens to undermine the pillars of national unity and stability. Society, by creating differences between individuals and regions on racial grounds, such as religion, color, race, language, political affiliation, and social class. Hate speech has become a means of implementing certain political agendas. The hate industry is considered one of the most important weapons used in psychological warfare, and the most important tools for dismantling social and political structures. Military wars target human lives, property, and material resources, while psychological wars aim to change the behavior of individuals, by influencing their thoughts, convictions, and beliefs.

Hatred is created through incitement, discrimination, intolerance, and racism, by falsifying facts, spreading rumors and misinformation, fabricating events, and slandering others. And manipulating minds. All of this results in a fertile environment that incubates hatred and fosters hostility and hatred. Ideas and beliefs turn into aggressive, extremist behavior, in which hatred appears in the form of political and religious slogans, positions, and speeches... and others.

Hate speech is the theoretical premise of serious crimes. Especially the crimes of genocide and various forms of violence. In this regard, Professor William Schabas says: "The road to genocide in Rwanda was paved with hate speech"¹.

All crimes that are committed against individuals or groups and are motivated by hatred, and push their perpetrators to commit the crime because of hatred, whatever it may be, are called “hate crimes.” Algeria witnessed one of the most heinous hate crimes in its history, which was committed on an ethnic basis, against the young man Jamal Ben Ismail, who was killed by a group of fanatical racists of Amazigh origin, who beat the victim to death, then amputated his limbs (leg and arm), slaughtered the body, and burned it in a public square, while they uttered racist and obscene words against the Arabs. It was widely condemned by the local and international public and was covered by various media outlets.

In this study, we seek to know the way in which the printed press in Algeria, represented by Echorouk newspaper, dealt with these events, by asking the following question: **How did Echorouk newspaper address the issue of the escalation of hate speech, which claimed the life of the young man Jamal Ben Ismail, following the forest fires it witnessed? Algeria in August 2021?**

Questions:

- What are the reasons that led to the escalation of hate speech in Algeria, according to Echorouk newspaper?
- What is the goal behind fueling hate speech in Algeria, according to Echorouk newspaper?
- What are the causes of forest fires during August 2021, according to Echorouk daily?
- Who are the actors revealed in Echorouk daily coverage in the killing of the young man Jamal Ben Ismail, and the forest fires, during the month of August 2021? How did you introduce them?
- What are the sources of information from which Echorouk newspaper obtained news about the subject of the study? How credible is it?
- What are the most common types of journalism used to provide content related to the subject of the study?
- What is the degree of focus on addressing hate speech and forest fires in Echorouk newspaper?

Study motivations:

The danger of hate speech, which could destabilize societies and dismantle national ties. And causing strife within and outside society. And destabilize the security and stability of countries. And the threat to national unity, which has escalated frighteningly in recent years. Its intensity increased during the forest fires in the state of Tizi Ouz, as it turned from mere racist rhetoric to extremist aggressive behavior, resulting in a heinous crime denounced by all of humanity. This is what prompted us to subject this phenomenon (the rise of hate speech) to study and analysis, to find out its sources and the reasons for its spread. And ways to limit and contain it.

- The killing of the young man Jamal Ben Ismail, due to racism and hate speech, and a state of local and international condemnation.

Algeria has not witnessed such fires since independence in 1962.

- The human and material losses caused by these fires.

The large number of these fires and their simultaneity raised doubts about their causes and goals.

- Doubts about the involvement of internal and external parties in igniting the fire of strife inside Algeria. By starting fires.

The study Objectives:

- Identify the method and manner in which the Algerian newspaper Echorouk dealt with it. The phenomenon of the escalation of hate speech and the events accompanying it in the summer of 2021. And the resulting violations against humanity, represented by the killing of the young man Jamal bin Ismail and the mutilation of his body because he was suspected of starting fires.
- Identifying the role of the Algerian national press in raising awareness of the dangers of hate speech on national unity and the stability of countries. And strive to confront and limit it. This is through Echorouk newspaper.
- Identify the real reasons for the outbreak of this huge and simultaneous number of fires, which Algeria has not witnessed since independence.
- Identifying the actors in these events according to Echorouk daily, the way they were presented to the reader, and the various roles they played.

The Study Importance:

Its importance stems from the importance of the events it addresses, as it addresses a heinous “hate crime,” which is considered a precedent in the history of crimes in Algeria, due to the frightening escalation of hate speech, which is sponsored by parties with separatist political agendas, seeking to achieve them on ethnic and cultural grounds.

In addition to the fires that affected forests in a number of regions at the same time, which Algeria had never witnessed before, and they occupied local and international public opinion throughout the period of time they took, in addition to the circumstances that surrounded them. And the doubts that swirled about its causes, and the involvement of internal and external parties with interests in its outbreak. And the huge human and material losses it caused.

The importance of the study also stems from the number of contradictions and conflicts between good and evil, between love and tolerance, hatred and discrimination, between unity and division, which were reported in the contents of Echorouk newspaper. In light of the spread of social media, which accelerates the spread of information and news, and the exchange and interaction with it, whether negatively or positively.

- The urgent need to conduct studies and research to analyze media content with the aim of evaluating the performance of the Algerian media in exceptional situations.

The study methodology and tools: Scientific study requires steps determined by the followed method. This is in order to reach accurate, objective results².

METHOD

Is the method that the researcher has to reach a certain result, through the correct organization of a series of numerous ideas. In order to prove it to others, so that we know it, this study falls within the framework of descriptive studies that reveal the essence of the pure. Descriptive studies do not stop at the point of collecting data, but rather their scope extends to

classifying the data and facts that are collected and recorded, interpreting and analyzing this data in a comprehensive manner, and extracting useful results and implications from it, leading to the possibility of issuing generalizations regarding the situation or the situation that the researcher is studying³.

Therefore, this study required us to use the descriptive approach. Because it accurately describes a phenomenon, by collecting, organizing, and analyzing data to reach the causes and factors controlling it and predict its behavior⁴.

The study population: The study population refers to the groups of institutions, people, units, and vocabulary⁵, that express the problem or essence of what is being studied⁶. In its spatial and temporal dimensions⁷. It is the sum of the sources in which the study is published or broadcast during the specified time frame⁸.

The study sample: The purposive sample was chosen, which is based on the intentional selection of representative vocabulary from others. For the information and data he is looking for⁹. It is also called “purposive,” “intentional,” or “typical” sampling, and it results from using the intentional method in choosing its vocabulary, with the intervention of the researcher in doing so¹⁰.

Our choice of purposive sample. The events studied were related to a limited period of time. It is the summer of 2021, exactly the month of August. Which witnessed the outbreak of massive fires on the 9th, which Algeria had never known before. However, media coverage of the events and the resulting hate crime began on August 11 and continued until August 28, and included 15 serial issues. This coverage was completely stopped in the last issues: August 29, 30, and 31. Knowing that Echorouk daily newspaper is not published on Fridays.

The study tools:

We relied on the content analysis tool, because it is the most suitable for analyzing media content.

Berelson defines it as: “one of the methods of scientific research that aims to objectively, systematically and quantitatively describe the content of a phenomenon or a material of communication”¹¹. We have used this tool in both its quantitative and qualitative forms. Quantitative analysis interprets data in quantitative terms. This is done by calculating the degree of repetition in different forms (space, time, word, sentence, topic), which are used as tangible materials in numerical measurement by their apparent presence in the studied material. Qualitative analysis is the objective distinction of previous quantitative results, focusing on the characteristics and qualities that distinguish things from each other¹².

Harold Lasswell’s, believes that content analysis aims to accurately and objectively describe what is said about a specific topic at a specific time”¹³.

Content analysis also defined as: “a systematic, quantitative, objective research method that clarifies the content of media material”¹⁴.

Analytical Units:

They are units of content that can be easily counted and measured, Its presence or absence and its recurrence or prominence provide indications that benefit the interpretation of quantitative results. Depending on the research objectives and hypotheses, the content is divided into units that can be counted and measured. The smallest is the word, the largest is the idea, then the subject and the vocabulary of publishing and radio¹⁵.

In this study, we have relied on the unity of the idea as a unit of counting and measurement. And the idea has no limits. Except for those that carry their meaning, which may be a phrase or a sentence. It may extend along the length of the vertebra. All content may consist of a single idea¹⁶: this is the most common and used unit in media research. Because dealing with the idea as a unit of analysis is useful in analyzing the trends and judgments that fall on the content of the media, because it is the unit that governs the writer's treatment of the other units¹⁷.

Analysis categories: There are two types of categories, content categories and form categories.

1- Categories of what was said (The content). We employed some of them that are in line with the requirements and objectives of our study, which are:

a) Category of actors:

This category helps in identifying people and groups that appear in the content as having played a role in carrying out certain actions. It can be used to reveal the knowledge of the makers and drivers of these events, those who help in their spread and expansion, and their beneficiaries and victims. Their nature and the nature of the conflict existing between them.

b) Source category:

This category answers the following question: To whom are the statements and statements attributed or what is the source to whom the content material is attributed? The amount of confidence in the information, statements or data provided by the source is determined according to the answers to the question¹⁸.

2- Categories of how it was said (The figure), we chose the category of journalistic genres and the category of publishing location (page ranking), which are the two categories that answer part of the questions raised.

A) Journalistic Types category:

That is, the arts of journalistic writing. It seeks to divide the content to be analyzed into written types such as: news, report, analytical article, reportage, column, investigation, commentary... and other journalistic types. This category is considered the soul of the newspaper, because it helps to deduce the elements of media treatment.

B) The content location at page category:

It shows the extent of interest in presenting the topic, as studying the location of the article being analyzed in the media outlet. And compare it to the relative importance of each site. According to the results of the reading, listening, and watching studies, we identified the degree of importance for each topic of analysis¹⁹.

The location of the content in the newspaper reflects its importance to the editorial board and the reader. The more important the events are, the more they are published on the front pages.

Study terms:

Hate speech: "It is any verbal, textual or graphic speech that works to spread hatred, incite hostility, sectarian, ethnic and political conflict, incite strife, and call for violence and discrimination on the basis of color, race, religion, sex, nationality, language...etc., and to differentiate between its members"²⁰.

The Algerian legislator defines it in the text of Law 20-5 issued on April 28, 2020 as: “All forms of expression that spread, encourage, or justify discrimination, as well as those that include a method of contempt, insult, hostility, hatred, or violence directed at a person or a group of people, provided that on the basis of sex, race, colour, descent, national or ethnic origin, language, geographical affiliation, disability or health condition”²¹.

The general climate of hate speech, according to Callamard, is based on inequality, exclusion, discrimination, and the claim of superiority over others, which provides an incubating environment for such ideas. On the other hand, it is necessary to declare solidarity with the victims, prevent the spread of this media propaganda discourse, and confront it with a discourse calling for tolerance, equality, and pluralism²².

From the previous definitions, we note that there is no unified definition of hate speech. The term is used to cover various forms of expression that aim to discriminate between individuals on racial, sectarian, religious, cultural, political, and even social, economic, and geographical grounds, with the intention of belittling and marginalizing them. The target may be an individual, or it may be a group of individuals or an entire community, and this speech may result in heinous crimes that are classified as hate crimes. Which has escalated remarkably in recent decades, with the widespread spread of social media.

Forest fires: also known as jungle, prairie, and forest fires, they are the ignition of fires in areas with dense vegetation, and they have devastating effects on the environment. They spread quickly, and may result from natural causes such as extreme heat, lightning, or because of human neglect by throwing away cigarette butts and cans. Glasses randomly, and may be due to criminal reasons. The spread of forest fires depends on the terrain, vegetation, and the nature of weather conditions. Forest fires can break out in a few seconds, turning the entire area into ash within minutes.

Algeria witnessed forest fires in the summer of 2021, which it had not witnessed since its independence in 1962. They caused huge human and material losses. A state of mourning was declared for 3 days.

Echorouk Newspaper: A national daily published in the Arabic language by the Echorouk Foundation. Its slogan is (Our opinion is right and may be wrong, and your opinion is wrong and may be right). It was founded in 1990 by the late Ali Fadil, the owner of the Echorouk Foundation. In 2005, it launched the first news website in Algeria. And the Arab world Echorouk newspaper is an independent newspaper not subject to any government agency. The number of journalists working inside its headquarters is 60, and 150 correspondents outside Algeria. The newspaper has branches in Europe²³.

Study results: The researcher presents the most important results of the study on four axes:

Actors, sources of information. Journalistic types. And the content location

The first axis: Actors:**Table 1: The Actors of the killing of a young man due to hate speech following forest fires**

Actors	Frequency	Percentage
Solidarity people	450	19.10%
Statesmen	414	17.57%
Victims	369	15.66%
Criminals	301	12.77%
Djamel ben Ismail	155	6.57%
Social media	127	5.39%
Hate speech	120	5.09%
A speech of calm and tolerance	110	4.66%
Mac movement	86	3.65%
Fires	86	3.65%
Foreign enemies	77	3.26%
Nour al-Din bin Ismail	46	1.95%
Notables, wise people, and sheikhs	15	0.63%
The total	2356	99.95%

In analyzing this category, the researcher relied on Greimas's practical model, which allows the analysis and study of the personality through its active role. It is not necessary for this character to be a living being or an individual. It may be an institution, a body, a group of individuals, a feeling, etc., as each central character is the subject of an action that it performs. A victory or success you achieve. Solution to a problem. For a difficult situation or a mediator between two contradictions, which is known as the functional advantage.

The character in this case possesses the characteristic or feature that helps him perform and achieve a task, either one of the axes, or all three together.

These axes, according to the Grimassian pragmatic model, divide the verb into 6 subjects:

The subject: He is the one who wants or does not want to be.

Goal: What the Actor seeks.

These two subjects represent the focus of the will in the action: *vouloir faire*.

Auxiliaries: factors that help the actor achieve his goal.

Opponents: Factors that hinder the actor from achieving his goal.

These two subjects represent the focus of the ability to act: *pouvoir faire*.

The sender: He is the one who commands action "prompts action."

Addressee: He is the beneficiary of this act.

These two subjects represent the focus of knowledge in the verb: savoir faire.

Through the contents of Echorouk newspaper, and according to the Gremasian model, we can define the roles of the actors as follows:

1) The actors who represent the axis of will in action: This axis includes: foreign enemies, the Mac separatist movement, and criminals

The goal: It is to create a state of instability in Algeria, after igniting a civil war between tribes and Arabs under the pretext of persecuting the minority and obliterating its identity. Which will inevitably lead to its weakening, especially in light of the current unstable international circumstances and the threats facing Algeria on the borders in particular.

The practical, driving actor: He is the one who has a program that he wants to achieve, and a goal that he seeks to reach.

Foreign enemies: Foreign enemies are represented by France, the traditional enemy, and Morocco, which it described as a bad, Zionist and lurking neighbor. Behind it is Israel, which is the practical actor driving all these events. These enemies are seeking to incite a civil war in Algeria to divide and weaken it. These are goals known to the public and private according to Echorouk newspaper, by seeking the help of the Mac separatist movement, which it described as traitorous, Agentic, malicious, and in collusion with the enemies. It also described its president, Farhat Mhenni, as a racist, a terrorist, and an outlaw. The latter, which was also described as a terrorist movement, has since its founding in 2001 been working to attack the people of the Kabylie region in general and Tizi Ouzou in particular - because it is the birthplace of Farhat Mhenni - with a speech that carries a lot of malice and hatred against everyone. What is Arab and belongs to Islam, under the pretext that the Amazigh are the owners of the land and the Arabs are the occupiers, and under the pretext that they have become a minority and that the Amazigh identity is in danger. It also publicly called for secession and the formation of armed militias to target citizens and state agencies. And preparatory orders for military defection and physical liquidation against the leaders of the army establishment and civil disobedience in preparation for complete chaos, or what they call “peaceful clash” with the security forces. All of them are criminal acts that strike public order to the core, according to Echorouk newspaper.

2) The Actors who represent the focus of the ability to act: they are the helpers and opponents

A) Assistants: They are those whom the practical, driving actor benefits from in implementing his program. They do not necessarily operate under the authority of this actor, but rather he may benefit from them indirectly. They are all represented by hate speech. Social media. Fires.

Hate speech: It can be considered the first assistant to the practical actor that drives the realization of the separatist plan, as through toxic and racist speech some of the youth of Tizi Ouzou were charged on ethnic and identity grounds to reject and exclude others over the course

of two decades, that is, since the year 2001, the date of the founding of the movement. Separatist Macs. These people believed that they were the owners of the land and that the Arabs were invaders and occupiers, and that the Islamic conquests were nothing but an occupation under the guise of spreading religion. They also believed in the superiority of the Amazigh element over the Arabs, and a feeling of superiority and hatred against everything that was not Amazigh was born in them.

Various social media outlets contributed to spreading toxic hate speech on a large scale. For example, taunting messages spread saying: “We have never seen a postman deliver a letter to its owners and stay with them,” as a metaphor for the first Muslim conquerors of North Africa. They came to spread the message of Muhammad and then Settle in the region.....Go to Saudi Arabia, this is your land...and other racist and obscene expressions.

The criminals, who were described as savages, primitives, murderers, and a group of deviants, belonging to the Mac separatist movement, took advantage of the fires, which were considered a small sample of the comprehensive conspiracy against Algeria, which the newspaper confirmed was contrived (because fires cannot occur in 13 states at the same time, except if it was planned and with criminal hands) to jump the law and bypass the security authorities, and try to implement the secession plan by turning against the policemen, imposing their logic and law, as if the Tizi Ouzou region is not part of this country, and is not subject to its laws, as they pulled the young man suspected of starting the fires from the hands of the men. The police, who sustained varying injuries, killed him and mutilated his body in a public square in Tizi Ouzou, without any physical evidence confirming his involvement. It later became clear that he was an innocent young man, an artist and musician, who came from his city of Miliana to help put out the fires.

B-) Opponents: They are those who seek to undermine the projects of the practical actor, spoil his plans, and replace them with new projects that serve their interests. They are represented by: statesmen, the people in solidarity, and social media. Jamal bin Ismail, speech of calm and tolerance, Nour al-Din bin Ismail, victims, notables, wise men, and sheikhs.

The statesmen, represented by: the police, have been frustrated. National Gendarmerie, army personnel, civil protection personnel and forest guards). Separatist plans, first by rescuing citizens affected by fires and afflicted people, and putting out the fires that claimed the lives of approximately 90 citizens, including 28 soldiers. Secondly, when the policemen sought to calm the atmosphere and refused to use weapons to disperse the criminals and prevent them from killing the young man, Jamal Ben Ismail, for fear of a breakdown in the security situation, but the criminals attacked them, took the victim from their hands, killed him, ate his body, and took selfies with it.

The People in Solidarity is the second opposition actor, who contributed strongly to thwarting the secession plans, and who gave the gift of one man to provide material, moral and psychological assistance to those affected by the fires. Many of them volunteered to travel to the afflicted states to help extinguish the fires, including the murdered young man Jamal Ben Ismail, which confirms that those who believe in hate speech and its racist principles are a minority with interests, while the majority believes in national unity, and that the nation is like a single body if a member is injured. The rest of his body suffered from sleeplessness and fever. Embodying the highest images of cohesion and brotherhood, refuting all racist speech that seeks to spread hatred and division.

Victims: This perpetrator includes: the afflicted who lost their homes, and the farmers and loyalists whose fields and livestock were burned, their source of livelihood. In addition to the number of dead, which numbered approximately 90, including 28 army personnel. These enormous enemies, including victims and those affected, revealed that criminals live by the logic of the end justifying the means, in order to achieve their sick separatist ambitions. To achieve their personal interests and goals, they do not hesitate to sabotage, destroy, and even kill. Farhat Mheni lost the image of a man defending the minority and the Amazigh identity. It turned out that he was an agent recruited to serve France, which hosted him on its territory and held its nationality. Natam Al-Makhzen, which is allied with Israel.

Jamal Ben Ismail, his murder was considered an ethnic hate crime par excellence. He was suspected of starting forest fires in Tizi Ouzou. It later became clear that he was an artist and musician of Arab origins who did not speak the Amazigh language from the city of Miliana. He volunteered with his peers to put out the fires, and despite being a victim, However, he is considered another powerful actor, before whom the separatists' plans were destroyed, as the brutal crime to which he was subjected - including beating, killing, amputation of organs, then slaughtering the body, burning it, and photographing it in a public square - simply because he was suspected of starting those fires. It revealed the true face of these criminals, who are in fact mentally ill, lack the lowest human values and morals, and represent a danger to society. Because the load of hatred that has accumulated within them for decades has blinded their vision and turned off their minds from seeing the truth. Here the magic turns against the magician and the ugly face of these fanatical criminals is revealed, and behind them is the Mac separatist movement supported by France, Morocco and Israel. It would be wrong to support them, follow their example, or cover up for them, which has prompted the entire society to ostracize and despise them, and to demand that retribution be applied to them so that they can serve as an example to those who consider them.

Social media played an effective role in exposing criminals and facilitating and accelerating their arrest, as the photos and videos documented the crime. It closed the door to evasion and denial of the crime in front of its perpetrators. She helped investigators find out the truth. Proving the innocence of the betrayed young man. Every person who has an account on social networking sites has become a private investigator seeking to discover the truth, so that those involved do not escape punishment. Thanks to social media, two attempts at illegal immigration by criminals involved in the murder of the late Jamal Ben Ismail were thwarted, one of them from the port of Skikda towards Europe, and the second from Oran towards Morocco.

Social media pioneers also had a great role in reporting the areas where fires broke out, as well as organizing volunteer campaigns to extinguish fires in the affected states. And fundraising campaigns, and conveying distress calls launched by citizens and charitable organizations.

These means also contributed to conveying what was happening in audio and video. First and foremost, especially in difficult and remote areas that the press cannot reach. Thanks to it, the recipient is constantly informed, from the heart of the event, of what is happening in the areas affected by the fire. It served as an alternative platform to traditional journalism, with its heroes being eyewitnesses.

The discourse of calm and tolerance: It was adopted by imams of mosques in Friday sermons, and by sheikhs of corners throughout the country. It was also adopted by professors and academics through various communication channels and platforms, as well as political figures of various stripes, emphasizing religious ties. And human and Islamic ethics, which emphasize that a Muslim is a brother to a Muslim, and that a Muslim is the one from whose tongue and hand people are safe. Accordingly, tongues must be refrained from spreading the toxins of hatred, grudges, racism, discrimination, and condescension, which God Almighty has forbidden, and which are among the attributes of Satan, the corruptor of the earth. They affirmed that the homeland there is a dire need for solidarity, unity, and rejection of violence and division, to stand up to the enemies lurking on every side. Calling for them to miss the opportunity.

Nour al-Din bin Ismail is the father of the late Jamal bin Ismail, whom Echorouk newspaper described as a hero, a balanced and patriotic man, and likened his patience and perseverance over the loss of his son to the patience of the prophets and righteous people, our master Jacob over the loss of our master Joseph, and the patience of the Messenger, may God bless him and grant him peace, over the loss of his youngest son, Abdul. God. Nour al-Din Ben Ismail, and his family behind him, were an important and decisive actor in eliminating strife in its infancy, calming the situation and healing the rift caused by the separatist Al-Malik movement and the criminals affiliated with it, when he said: The Algerians are brothers, and the criminals only represent themselves. They do not represent the people of the Kabylie region, who are known for their noble morals. He refused to take revenge for the death of his betrayed son, leaving justice to take its course.

Notables, wise men and Old men: led by the notables of the state of Tizi Ouzou and its wise men, including imams, university professors, heads of associations, and sheikhs of corners from all parts of the country, similar to the officials of the Association of Muslim Scholars, they came to the city of Miliana, the birthplace of the deceased, to offer their condolences and attend the funeral of the deceased Jamal Ben Ismail. We apologize for the heinous crime to which the victim was subjected, by some young people devoid of all human and moral values, young people charged with poisonous and reckless rhetoric, calling for curbing the extremist and separatist voices that push towards rot and strife. They also handed over blood money to the family of the dead man, as is customary in the Islamic religion. In an attempt to alleviate the grief of the bereaved family regarding their son, console them in their great affliction, and support them in such difficult times. This gesture, which was described as kind, won the approval of the family of the deceased and the residents of the city of Miliana, and contributed to absorbing their anger and the anger of all Algerians, and alleviated the tense atmosphere that the Algerians had experienced over the course of days. It was also considered a good initiative to correct matters and not leave room for adventurers and criminals to confuse Algerians on worthless linguistic and ethnic grounds.

In the end we can say:

The practical actor driving the events, who is not pure in public, represented by the foreign enemies, was able to bring his plan to life on the ground, with the help of the Mac separatist movement, which chose a group of deviant youth criminals charged with hate speech to ignite the fires of fires in the forests, and the fires of strife and division between members of one people. By assassinating the young man Jamal bin Ismail in a brutal manner, imposing their own law, and these people almost succeeded in implementing their plan in full, had it not been for the acumen of the statesmen, the people in solidarity, and the notables, wise people,

and sheikhs, who adopted the discourse of calm and tolerance, led by the father of the late Nour al-Din bin Ismail, who averted the strife. He refused to take revenge, in addition to the victims who died during these fires and those affected by them, and the brutal crime committed, which were factors that exposed the nature of these people, and revealed their true nature that is hostile to the homeland and to popular and national unity. In addition to the fact that the supporting actor was not strong enough to help achieve the goal. This actor had the will to act, and worked to achieve his goal, but his project did not take place as he had planned, so he actually lost the axis of know-how, and the balance of power was tipped in favor of the opposition actor who tipped the balance of power in his favor, renewing the spirit of brotherhood and solidarity in the souls of the Algerians, who gave the gift of one man to thwart the conspiracy. With the help of statesmen, they harnessed all means to achieve this, especially social media.

It should be noted that social media played two fundamental roles in these events: it was an actor that assisted the practical actor who drove it (the nation's enemies) and an actor opposing it at the same time, as it was used to spread hate speech on the largest scale, which contributed to fueling hatred, racism, and the spirit of revenge. It also worked to uncover those involved in the heinous crime that claimed the life of Jamal bin Ismail. Therefore, social media is a double-edged sword. The individual is the only one responsible for the results of his uses, either as a tool for construction or as a tool for demolition. Therefore, his use must be rationalized in accordance with what morals and principles dictate. This can only be achieved through moral education imbued with human values, and informational education that helps individuals rationalize their use of these means, which have resulted from technical progress.

The second axis: Sources of information

Table 02: Represents the sources of information approved by the newspaper Editorial

Sources of information	Frequency	Percentage
Reporters	101	43.91%
Declaration	53	23.04%
Press releases	39	16.95%
Social media	20	8.69%
Our sources are without detail	07	3.04%
Press conference	03	2.60%
Speech of the President of the Republic	02	0.86%
Algerian News Agency	01	0.43%
National Radio	01	0.43%
The total	230	99.95%

We noticed from the table that Echorouk newspaper relied on live field coverage of events, with a large percentage of 43.91%, which means that it is keen to provide a service from the middle of the event with reliable sources, since the press reporter is the source.

The press release had a rating of 23.04%, and it is known that the press release is used to give more details and clarifications, which means that the newspaper sought to provide a complete briefing on the events. Most of the statements were issued by specialists in the field of fires and officials in the state sectors to provide more information about the areas of fire expansion, losses. Materiality, humanity, and the development of the course of events. Press releases amounted to 16.95%, which is a high percentage, and most of them were issued by state institutions and official and community bodies, which adopted them to present various

statistics. They were also used to denounce and denounce the events taking place, such as forest fires and the heinous crime committed.

Social media was strongly used as sources of information, reaching a percentage of 8.69%, and it varied between personal accounts, such as the president's Twitter account, and websites of official institutions. This is due to the advantages it enjoys, including immediate access to information and the possibility of wide dissemination.

The coverage, in which the source was not mentioned in detail, reached a percentage of 3.04%, but it is a very small percentage compared to the previous sources that are considered more reliable, which represented 97%, which means that the newspaper succeeded in providing correct and accurate information, as the situation that the country is witnessing does not allow Error or questionable information.

The percentage of press conferences reached 2.60%, and the three press conferences were limited to news of the investigations into the murder of the young man Jamal Ben Ismail, as they were activated by judicial police officials, to reveal the circumstances of the heinous crime and those involved in it. They also reported their live testimonies about the details of the crime. It was broadcast live on the national television channel.

The speech of the President of the Republic was used as a source of information with a percentage of 0.86%, as he expressed his regret for the fires that were occurring and promised to follow up on the criminals, as they were proven to be fabricated criminal operations. He offered his condolences and solidarity to the families of the victims, and declared a period of mourning for 3 days out of mercy for their souls.

The Algerian News Agency and the National Radio were relied upon at a rate of 0.43%, which is a very small percentage, ranking last, and this indicates the decline of these sources, which are considered traditional. Especially for the news agencies that were previously at the top of the list of approved sources of information, in order to develop new sources that provide Fast, free and around-the-clock services. Similar to the official websites of various institutions, and the personal accounts of famous and active figures. On social networking sites, which in this study ranked fourth in terms of reliance on them.

Finally, we can say that it was clear the effort of those responsible for Echorouk newspaper to investigate the sources of its information, and the extent of its reliability and accuracy. It obtained 97% of its news from informed primary sources. And others from the field of events. In many cases, it is accompanied by accurate numbers and statistics, which reflects the high professionalism of the press team and officials in dealing with these events. And the credibility of the newspaper.

The third axis: Journalism Types

Table No. 03: Represents the types of journalism in the newspaper contents

Journalism Types	Frequency	Percentage
Press report	104	47.70%
Press release	75	34.40%
Newspaper article	17	7.79%
Reportage	12	5.50%
Press release	10	4.58%
The total	218	99.97%

The number of coverage that dealt with the subject of the study reached 218 coverage, presented in several journalistic formats, and distributed over 15 issues, in which the newspaper relied on the two types of press report and news in the largest proportion, estimated at 47.70% and 34.40% for each one, respectively, which reflects the newspaper's interest in making The reader is informed of everything new. In view of the acceleration of events and the expansion of their scope, because these two types provide a large number of information and details, the newspaper's priority is to remove confusion about the events and cut off rumors, especially after the great escalation of hate speech and what resulted from it, in addition to the essentially news nature of the newspaper.

The percentage of reliance on intellectual types was 7.97%, represented in the newspaper article, which is a significant percentage, due to the newspaper's interest in framing and directing the reading public, and instilling in it values and convictions. Discussing the issue of hate speech as a social, human and moral purity, alien to our society, has become worrying due to its breadth, multifaceted dimensions and threat to national unity and popular cohesion. The newspaper has made clear in the published articles its view of the events. By analyzing and dissecting the facts, and trying to find out their true causes and motives, I also suggested ways to address them.

The newspaper relied on press reportage at a rate of 5.50%. While the percentage of reliance on the press release was 4.58%, which is weak percentages. This is due to the nature of the news newspaper, as well as the rapid developments witnessed by events. As we mentioned earlier.

The fourth axis: The Page number and arrangement of the content

Table No. 04: Represents the number and order of the page

The Page number and arrangement of the content	Frequency	Percentage
3	37	16.97%
7	31	14.22%
2	23	10.55%
8	20	9.17%
5	17	7.79%
6	17	7.79%
9	14	6.42%
4	11	5.04%
24	11	5.04%
13	10	4.58%
11	08	3.66%
12	04	1.83%
16	03	1.37%
21	03	1.37%
14	02	0.91%
17	02	0.91%
20	02	0.91%
19	01	0.45%
The Total	218	97.6%

We have categorized the pages as follows:

The first pages included: the second, third, and fourth pages, and the percentage of publishing the contents subject of the study was: 32.56% (3 pages only). The inner pages included: the pages starting from the fifth page (5) to page No. 12 (7 pages), and the percentage of publishing the contents was Subject of study: 50.88%. And the last pages, and the pages from page No. 13 to page No. 24 were combined. The percentage of publication of the contents subject of the study was: 14.16% (7 pages).

The researcher believes that the front pages took the lead in spreading the topic of hate speech and fires, if we compare the percentage of content published in these pages (32.56%) with the number of pages that dealt with the topic of the study (which is only 3 pages).

The internal pages ranked second with a percentage of 50.88% in publishing news of hate speech and fires, while the back pages ranked last with a percentage of 14.16%.

The front and internal pages occupying the forefront in publishing the subject of the study is due to the importance of the topic. And his sensitivity at the same time, as he dealt with a heinous hate crime, was the result of the escalation of hate speech and discrimination, adopted and fueled by hostile foreign parties, and other puppet local parties seeking separation on ethnic grounds, speech that would threaten national unity and harm popular cohesion, if it was not contained. And eliminate it with strict deterrent methods, in addition to the huge material and human losses that resulted from these events, and because of them, a 3-day national mourning was declared.

The front and inner pages are considered more readable by readers, because they contain a lot of news. And the most important of them.

CONCLUSION

Echorouk newspaper attached great importance to these events. It devoted 218 media coverage to them, distributed over 15 issues, with an average of 14.53 % coverage per issue. Media coverage began immediately after the outbreak of fires on August 11, and then increased in intensity after the hate crime that occurred in Tizi Ouzou. The coverage ended with the completion of the investigations and the arrest of the criminals involved in the assassination on August 28. The causes of the crime were attributed to the escalation of hate speech and violence that is known in the Tizi Ouzou region in particular, which moved from being merely a racist mobilization speech in which the voice of wisdom was absent, to aggressive, violent behavior behind it. Heinous crime.

Echorouk newspaper reports what happened to the Mac separatist movement headed by Farhat Mhanni, which was founded in 2001. The latter worked to instill the youth of the region with racist and supremacist ideas over the course of two decades, convincing them that they are the owners of the land, and that the Muslim Arabs are occupiers hiding behind the cloak of Islamic conquests. They must return to the Arabian Peninsula. This movement also called for the establishment of armed militias and the declaration of self-rule in the Kabylie region, and demanded the liquidation of army leaders in Algeria.

The process of creating forest fires was the gateway through which the Mac separatist movement entered, in an attempt to implement its separatist plan and impose its law, through a group of young people who believe in its poisonous slogan and are charged with pathological hate speech. According to the newspaper, fires cannot break out in 13 states in a day and at the

same time, and in places with very difficult terrain, in the middle of forests and in mountainous heights, unless it is carried out by an active force.

The MAC movement, headed by Farhat Mhenni, was nothing but a front for other parties, represented by France, the traditional enemy, Morocco, and behind it Israel, which has become a real threat to our western borders. These parties are the ones who benefit, according to Echorouk newspaper, from weakening Algeria and igniting a civil war in it, so that it can from imposing certain agendas, especially intense international situations. And keeping Algeria away from playing a role on the international scene.

Echorouk newspaper investigated its news sources very carefully. The percentage of known and reliable sources reached more than 97% of the approved sources, and most of them were from its informed primary sources, or from correspondents who served as eyewitnesses. The researcher attributes this to the sensitivity of the issue and its connection to national unity. There is no room for error, and no room for questionable or false news, because it may further aggravate the situation and put the credibility and objectivity of the newspaper at risk. In addition to the newspaper's national affiliation, which it does not risk, in the face of these charged circumstances.

We also noticed a significant decline in reliance on traditional sources of information, such as news agencies, radio, and television channels, all of which came with only one repetition. While reliance on social media as sources of news and information increased, through the official accounts of officials, decision-makers and celebrities on Facebook, Instagram, Twitter...etc. and the websites of institutions from various sectors that were dedicated to covering these events, such as charitable and governmental institutions. ...etc.

The types of news and report journalism were the most relied upon by the newspaper, because it was keen to convey information and bring the reader along with the events, which were accelerating, knowing that the two types of journalistic news and report are the ones most capable of performing the media function by conveying a large amount of information.

Although the newspaper is primarily a news newspaper, it relied on intellectual genres remarkably (17 newspaper articles) at a rate of 1.33% per issue, which means that all issues contained at least a newspaper article, through which it sought to frame the reader and correct his thoughts. And instilling moral and human values in it, through which Tahira dissected the rise of hate speech, with the words of journalists and academic doctors from various disciplines, such as psychology and sociology, to find out its causes, motives, dangers and consequences.

The newspaper confirmed that if Tahira does not address hate speech from its roots and firmly, it will have very dire consequences, on individuals, society and the state, and the best example of this is the heinous hate crime, in which the late Jamal Ben Ismail fell victim in Tizi Ouzou, on an ethnic basis. This can only be achieved by strictly applying the laws criminalizing racism, hate speech and discrimination, to everyone, without exception. And spreading the discourse of love, tolerance, and acceptance of others, and returning to the teachings of our true Islamic religion, and the Sunnah of our Noble Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace, who said: "A Muslim is one from whose tongue and hand Muslims are safe.." ²⁵.

The real perpetrators of these events, and the actual instigators of them, were unclear in public. They had no direct role. They were purified through their plans only, but the newspaper revealed and identified them, and called them lurking enemies, namely France, Morocco, and behind them Israel. The newspaper considered them dangerous actors threatening the unity of the nation. Because their goal is to ignite a civil war in Algeria to weaken it, preoccupy it with

internal problems, and exclude it from playing a pivotal role in the international arena that is witnessing radical changes in the balance of power.

These actors driving the events encouraged the parties purged at the forefront, represented by the MAC movement, which has separatist ambitions on ethnic and cultural grounds, to implement its plans with the help of a group of people charged with discriminatory racist discourses, exploiting other factors such as social media and forest fires.

However, the plan to secede and destabilize Algeria did not succeed, first because of the crimes committed in order to achieve this goal, starting with setting fires and ending with the horrific killing of an innocent young man, who volunteered to put out the fires, in addition to the victims who died during the fires, and the material losses and damages that were incurred. It affected the environment, all of which revealed the ugly face of Farhat Mohani, the tyranny of personal interests, and individual ambition over lofty principles, and secondly, the statesmen, the people, the rational people, and the family of the murdered, who confronted this plan, as they sparked sedition in its infancy, thus overpowering the discourse of love, tolerance, and brotherhood, and the security authorities were able to arrest him. Criminals were found within days with the help of social media, and 49 of them were sentenced to death. Bringing the curtain down on one of the most heinous hate crimes. Which shook the Algerian and international community, and emphasized the danger of hate speech, which has been escalating in recent decades.

Through this study, we noticed that social media played a fundamental role in these events, as it was exploited to spread hate speech on a large scale, through pictures, video clips, slogans, and even through jokes and cartoons, which contain inflammatory phrases against Arabs, and expressions It was offensive and contained a lot of discrimination and contempt. It also conveyed the details of the heinous crime that occurred in Tizi Ouz, and the selfie photos that were taken with the corpse and the criminals celebrating their heinous act. At the same time, these means were used to send relief calls during the fires, to collect donations, and distribute them. They also conveyed images of solidarity. Among the people, it helped security personnel identify those involved in the crime, and expedited the task of arresting them.

From this we are certain that man is the only one responsible for the nature of the use of technology, whether for good or evil. In order to benefit from these continuous technological developments in a way that makes them a blessing in our lives, we must rationalize their use and activate self-control to prevent us from making mistakes. This can only be achieved through comprehensive media education, sponsored by socialization institutions at various age levels.

Foot Notes

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